

AUSTRIAN
AGENCY FOR
RESEARCH
INTEGRITY

CoARA Action Plan

by the Austrian Agency for
Research Integrity (ÖAWI)

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1. History and Remit of the ÖAWI

Established as an independent association in 2008, the Austrian Agency for Research Integrity's (ÖAWI) primary remit is to act as a national body to support the development of research integrity principles and the upholding of good research practice among higher education institutions, research institutions, and funding bodies in Austria. Conceived by 16 founding members, membership of the ÖAWI has now grown to more than 70 institutions including all public universities in Austria, as well as private universities, universities of applied sciences, non-university research institutions, research funding agencies and the Federal Ministry for Women, Science and Research.

The ÖAWI supports its members in practicing research integrity and good research practice via two approaches. With the assistance of an international commission of independent experts, the ÖAWI is dedicated to advising on and investigating cases of suspected research misconduct. The ÖAWI also supports members by providing advice, training and awareness raising of best practices in research integrity. As a member of various international networks and a collaborating partner in grant based projects, the ÖAWI itself contributes to wider discussions and agenda setting regarding best practice in research, sharing these insights with its members and the wider Austrian research community.

2. The ÖAWI and CoARA

As a national body supporting member institutions, the ÖAWI does not participate in decisions on recruitment, promotion, grant or funding allocation, meaning not all aspects of the CoARA Commitments are applicable to the Agency's work. However, as the ÖAWI works to support integrity in research, in line with CoARA's basic principles, the Agency has an important role in education and awareness raising, guiding Austrian institutions towards research assessment reform. As of publication, just over 15% of the ÖAWI's member institutions are CoARA signatories.

With CoARA's principles for overarching conditions being heavily aligned with the ÖAWI's own remit, particularly with regard to compliance with integrity rules and practices, the ÖAWI can be seen as a supporting institution to educate its members on best practice, which these members may in turn use to inform their assessment criteria.

Similarly, with many of the principles for assessment criteria and practice, particularly with regards to research quality, being based on the principles of good scientific practice, there is heavy overlap between CoARA and the ÖAWI's work. The ÖAWI runs trainings and raises awareness on good research practice which members can also use to shape their assessment criteria, having been informed of what best practice should look like in research.

As a result of the overlap between the ÖAWI's work and the CoARA principles, the first section of this report will assess current ÖAWI practices which support education and raising awareness among our membership. The second half of the report explores potential steps the ÖAWI may take to foster greater awareness and collaboration on research assessment reform within the Austrian research community.

3. Current Supporting Actions

3.1. Train the Trainer Course + Tailored Workshops

The ÖAWI runs annual two-day train-the-trainer (TtT) workshops (one in English, and one in German) open to all members. The ÖAWI also provides ad hoc tailored workshops according to member requests and ÖAWI capacity. Content focuses on developing research integrity and good research practice competencies among relevant stakeholders which they in turn are encouraged to share with others in their institution.

In their content and structure, the Train the Trainer programme and tailored workshops contribute to commitments 1, 3, 5, 7 and 8.

Commitment 1: Content raises general awareness of alternative forms of research assessment, encourages celebration of robust, open, transparent and inclusive research practices and explores best practice in leadership, training, supervision and mentoring.

Commitment 3: As part of the session on publication, trainers actively encourage participants to move away from the h-index and journal related metrics, to instead assess publications based on the quality of the research and the researcher.

Commitments 5 and 7: Workshops function as both awareness raising and part of the education and training process for staff involved in research assessment. They are also a space to promote the CoARA project and commitments themselves, encouraging more of our members to sign the pledge.

Commitment 8: Workshops are structured around participant exchange and mutual learning, providing a collaborative space for participants to potentially discuss research assessment reform and best practices in research.

3.2. Shared Documentation

In a section of the ÖAWI website, useful documentation for supporting research integrity is provided for any visitor to download. Documentation includes statements from the World Conference on Research Integrity as well as the CoARA principles and, thereby, contributes to the awareness raising aspects of CoARA and Commitments 1, 5 and 7.

3.3. Network and Project Participation

Being an active member in networks such as ENRIO (European Network of Research Integrity Offices) and regularly participating in international research integrity related projects, the ÖAWI is involved in agenda setting on best practice and shaping the criteria on which research is judged. The Agency's participation in these networks and projects keeps the ÖAWI abreast

of current developments and future avenues of exploration at global, European and national levels, with the ability to promote the CoARA commitments within such meetings.

4. Future Supporting Actions

4.1. Resource Hub

As part of the development of our digital offerings and the re-design of the website, the ÖAWI plans to create a new online resource hub. The resource hub will be structured around key themes to keep documentation organised and findable, with research assessment reform potentially incorporated as a theme in this organisational structure.

4.2. eLearning Resources

The development of eLearning resources and videos are also planned as part of the ÖAWI's digital redesign. In developing the content of these videos, the themes of the CoARA principles and commitments could be incorporated.

4.3. Newsletter

To celebrate developments in the ÖAWI's work related to research assessment reform, as well as best practice among members, the ÖAWI can use its newsletter to communicate these to its members and subscribers.

4.4. Event Series

The ÖAWI runs a regular event series, Research Integrity: Aktuell (RI:A), inviting guest speakers to give short presentations on themes related to research integrity which all ÖAWI members are welcome to attend. As part of future offerings, an event could be organised to promote the CoARA commitments and research assessment reform more broadly, as well as encouraging non-signatories to join the Coalition.

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Austrian Agency for Research Integrity

Landstraßer Hauptstraße 9 | 21, 1030 Vienna

www.oewi.at

Tel.: 01/7106821

E-Mail: office@oewi.at